

TEENAGE PREGNANCY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL FEMALE STUDENTS IN IGBO-ETITI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, ENUGU STATE

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Abstract: The study investigated Teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government area, Enugu State. Three research questions and one hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. Descriptive research design was adopted for the study. A sample of 312 female students was used for the study which was drawn from a population of 6000 female students from 15 public secondary schools using a two-stage sampling procedure. A structured questionnaire titled "Teenage Pregnancy Questionnaire (TPQ)" which was validated by three experts, two of which were from Human kinetics and Health Education Department and one from the Department of Maths and Computer was used for data collection. Data collected with the help of three research assistants were analyzed using frequency count and percentages. The findings revealed among others that; peer group pressure, poverty and lack of parental care were factors responsible for teenage pregnancy, drop out of school, low educational achievement and unplanned marriage are consequences of teenage pregnancy and use of contraceptives, guidance and counseling are ways to control teenage pregnancy among secondary schools students in Igbo-Etiti LGA. It was concluded that poverty, peer group pressure and lack of parental control for their female wards are responsible for teenage pregnancy among female students in Igbo-Etiti LGA. Based on the conclusion, it was recommended among others that the State Government through the Post Primary School Management Board, Enugu State should organize seminars and workshops for female secondary school students on the causes, consequences and control measures of teenage pregnancy among the female students.

Keywords: Teenager, teenage pregnancy, secondary school teenage students.

Introduction

Teenage pregnancy is a major public health issue. The problem confront many high, middle and low income countries globally. Teenage or adolescent pregnancy means pregnancy in women between 10 to 19 years. Teenage pregnancy has been called an epidemic worldwide. Teenagers are the greatest number of people found in most secondary schools. They are those young persons within the age of 10 and 19 years. According to Living Webster Encyclopedic dictionary of the English Language (2014), these years fall within the adolescent period, at this period the individual seeks for those ties within the opposite sex and to secure identity. These behaviours may not be of their biological setting rather of societal expectations. As a result of the biological

instinct at this period, they may have high tendency to indulge in pre-marital sex, which may leave her in perpetual regret.

This health problem seems to be popular among the female teenagers in the forms of teenage pregnancy (Festus, 2019). These young people may be entangled in this due to the hindrance which may erupt as a result of exhibition of obnoxious behaviour encouraged by the media. Globally, million women under the age of 20 give birth representing up to one-fifth of all births and 529,000 women die due to pregnancy and child birth related complications every year (Dev Raj.Rabi, Arnudha, Van Teijlingen & Chapman, 2016). Teenage pregnancy is a major concern to world communities with U.S being at the top with almost 1, 000,000 teenage pregnancies each year (Williams, 2022). The United State has highest pregnancy and births among adolescents (Coley & Lansdale 2017). According to the inter-pres service (2021), the global rate for teenage pregnancy for the year 2011 was 52, 9 pregnancies, per 1, 000 female adolescent. In 2000, the total number of teenage pregnancies in the United State was 821, 81 (84 pregnancies per 1000 people), as compared to Canada whose total rate of teenage pregnancies in 2000) was 38 pregnancies per 1000 people (Chengaxhu 2020).

In England there are nearly 90, 000 teenage conceptions per year around 1 7,700 girls under the age of 16 and 2,200 of girls aged 14 or under (Holgate Evans & Yuen, 2021). The department of health (United Kingdom) in Macleod (2020) reported that in England and Wales, more women in their early twenties find themselves with unwanted pregnancies that end in abortion. The United State has the highest teenage birth rate of all developed countries (Crosson-Tower, 2015). According to Inter-Press service (April, 2015), teenage pregnancy accounted for 40 percent of maternal deaths in Sierra Leone where early marriage is supported by traditional practice. Seventy percent (70%) teenage girls' in Sierra Leone' are married (World Health Organization, 2018).

The W.H.O figures showed that the global average number of pregnancies for every 1, 000 girls in the 15-19 age group is 65.

The rate of early marriage and pregnancy has decreased sharply in Indonesia and Malaysia, although it remains relatively high in the former. In African, the sexual behaviour of urban adolescents in Nigeria and Liberia is now very similar to that of people in the same age category in the USA and Europe (UNICEF, 2017). In the same continent (Arica), girls are often married at a younger age and are under pressure to give birth to children. According to (UNICEF, 2017) Bangladesh has aimed 16 percent of fifteen-year old. Girls who are pregnant or already have children, whereas 75 percent of girls in the Democratic Republic of Congo and over half of all girls in Afghanistan and Bangladesh are married before the age of 13. The survey conducted by a leading international organization called "Save the Children" stated that annually 13million children are born to women under the age of 16 years and more than 90 percent in developing countries. It is also that the highest rate of teenage pregnancy in the world was found in the sub Saharan African (Achu, 2016). Being a teenager is one of the most wonderful and exciting times, as they grow from childhood to adulthood, it can be confusing and disturbing time too. At this period, young person begin to have their own opinion about what to do, what they want, what they want to wear, where to go and how to behave. This period is regarded as a period/time of increased emotional tension resulting from physical and psychological change in the child (Alkinson, 2021). The above assertion further explained that the adolescent developmental tasks represent the total problems and must be solved during the transition from childhood to adulthood.

Teenage pregnancy has claimed the lives of many female students in Nigeria secondary schools. Nzeagu (2016) noted that a degree of desperation follows and abortion either self-administered, or done by an unqualified person (doctor) is often considered. Health professionals are not consulted for pregnancy test, care or termination of fetus which often result because of the teenagers want to free herself from rejection by relatives and friends as well the shame the pregnancy would bring to her and the family.

Research shows that teenage pregnancy could result due to various factors which include; economic factors such as quest for materialism, insufficient money for essential provisions and needs. Moreover, a social factor is another factor that contributes to teenage pregnancy, for example, influences of peer -group, unrealistic false marriage promises from boys and sexual permissiveness in the society, (Duvall, 2018). Religious factors also contribute to teenage pregnancy like lack of moral disciplines, lack of fear of God, lack of moral instruction. Nevertheless educational factors cannot be over emphasize for instance, the system of day school which permits students to roam about without supervision by the school authority. Ignorance of safe and unsafe period of menstrual cycle, insufficient sex education and lack of knowledge of family planning practices. Also, cultural factors also contributes to teenage pregnancy and they are as follows; inability of parent to discuss sex matters with their children's, quest for early marriage among girls.

Teenage pregnancy has it consequences such as unable to finish their education. It also leads to being infected with sexual transmitted infections (STIs) to young people in secondary school and outside school. Apart from medical consequence, lower access to higher education, high divorce rates, premature death of women, population growth, weak and unhealthy children and single motherhood are all negative consequence of teenage pregnancy.

Furthermore, teenage pregnancy brings shame and distress to the teenagers and their parent, it also result to discrimination among his or her peer group. Another consequence of teenage pregnancy is that they are being deprived of the right to choose their life partner, it becomes necessary to carry out this study on teenage pregnancy, so as to help the teenager girls avoid been victims of unwanted pregnancy. It is against this background that the researcher intends to find out teenage pregnancy among secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government of Enugu State.

In these recent years, there is high incidence of teenage pregnancies in our society. Teenage pregnancy has made some of young girls to lose their life through abortion which is done by unqualified doctors. Most teenagers who are involved in this act are usually unable to complete their education, teenage pregnancy is generally regarded as social and moral problems which often results in shame and distress to the teenagers and most often abortion and consequently death. This is worrisome, hence the need for the study.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the teenage pregnancy among secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area of Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- 1 Find out the factors responsible for teenage pregnancy among secondary schools students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area of Enugu State.
2. Determine the consequences of teenage pregnancy among secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area of Enugu State

3. Find out possible control measures of teenage pregnancy as perceived by secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area of Enugu State. Of teenage pregnancy. It also looks at parents reactions to teenage pregnancy.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study.

1. What are the factors responsible for teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area of Enugu State?

2. What are the consequences of teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area of Enugu State?

3. What are possible control measures to teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area of Enugu State?

Method.

Research Design was used because it facilitates the description of situation in its current state and solicits information directly from the respondents, which makes the information from 000 female students from 15 secondary schools in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area of Enugu state. The sample size for the study consisted of 312 students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area of Enugu state which was determined by the use of Taro Yamane (1964) formula. Two-stage sampling procedure was used to draw the sample. Firstly, 6 schools were sampled out of 15 secondary schools in the area using simple random sampling technique. Secondly, also simple random sampling techniques was used to draw 52 students from the selected 6 secondary schools making a total of 312 students.

A structured questionnaire titled “Teenage Pregnancy Questionnaire (TPQ)” was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire consists of two sections -A and B. Section A contained items that solicit information on the personal data of the respondents. Section B has 4 parts, which carry a two point rating scale of “yes” and “no” that deals on teenage pregnancy.

The validation of the research instrument was done by 3 experts, 2 from the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education and 1 from the Department of Maths and Computer, all in Faculty of Education. Reliability of the instrument was established through the use of Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded reliability value of 0.75 confirming the reliability of the instrument. The questionnaire was administered on the sport with the help of 3 trained research assistants. Three hundred and twelve (312) copies of the instruments were administered on the sampled female students but 300 was returned and qualified for analysis,

The data collected were analysed using frequency counts and percentages.

Results

Research Question1: What are the factors responsible for teenage pregnancy?

Among secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area Enugu State.

The above research question was answered using the responses of secondary school student as shown in table one below.

Table 1: Percentage Response Distributions of the Respondents on Factors Responsible for Teenage Pregnancy among Female sec Secondary Schools students in Igbo-Etiti LGA

S/N	Items	YES	%	NO	%	Dec
1.	Peer pressure	210	70	90	30	Agree
2.	Influence of pornographic films	78	25	222	75	Disagree
3.	Poverty	200	67	100	33	Agree
4.	Lack of sex education	62	21	238	79	Disagree
5.	Lack of self-control	98	33	202	67	Disagree
6	Lack of parental care	187	62	113	38	Agree
7	7 Broken homes	78	25	224	75	Disagree
	7 Broken homes	78	25	224	75	Disagree

Table 1 shows 7 factors responsible for teenage pregnancy of female sec school students.

The table indicates that 3 of the items (peer group pressure, poverty and lack of parental care) are factors responsible for teenage pregnancy. This is shown by their percentage of 70%, 67% and 62% respectively.

Research question 2

What are consequences of teenage pregnancy among secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area Enugu State?

Table 2: Percentage Response Distribution of the Respondents on

Consequences of Teenage Pregnancy among Female Secondary Schools Students in Igbo-Etiti LGA

S/N	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%	Dec
8.	Rejections by parents	102	34	198	66	Disagree
9.	Poor production of res blood call	62	21	238	79	Disagree
10.	Drop out from school	220	73	80	27	Agree
11.	Infection (STI)	85	28	215	72	Disagree
12.	Low educational achievement	281	94	19	6	Agree
13.	High rate infant mortality	83	8	292	97	Disagree
14.	Unplanned marriage	284	95	16	5	Agree

Table 2 shows 7 items on consequences of teenage pregnancy of female sec school students. The table indicates that 3 of the items (Drop out of school, low educational achievement and unplanned marriage) are consequences of teenage pregnancy.

Research question 3:

What are possible control measures to teenage pregnancy in secondary schools?

Table 3: Percentage Response Distribution of the Respondents on Control Measures of Teenage Pregnancy among Female Secondary School students in Igbo-Etiti LGA.

S/N	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%	Decision
19.	Parent cares and attends to their children	36	12	240	80	Disagree
20.	Use of contraception	220	73	80	27	Agree
21.	Guidance and counseling	208	69	92	31	Agree
22.	Avoidance of bad friends	264	88	36	12	Agree
23.	Through religious organization	102	34	98	66	Disagree
24.	Attending on seminars teenage Pregnancy	62	21	238	79	Disagree
25.	Through complete abstinence	98	33	202	67	Disagree

Table 3 shows 7 items on control measures to teenage pregnancy of female sec school students. The table indicates that 3 of the 7 items (use of contraceptives, guidance and counseling and avoidance of bad friends) are control measures to teenage pregnancy

Discussion of the Findings

The finding pertaining to research question 1 showed that Peer group pressure, poverty and lack of parental care are factors responsible for teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students in Igbo- Etiti Local Government Area, Enugu State. This findings, agree with the views of Golden (2008) who stated that peer group influence is a critical factor influencing the behavior of teenagers especially sex behaviours. They provide the norms or standards of operations for teenage girls especially when their parents fails to discuss sex issues with them. Meanwhile, Ojo and Femi (2008), noted that most teenagers find accommodations for themselves early in life. This exposes them to rich men for financial gains, which may lead to pregnancy by sleeping with these men in exchange of money

The findings pertaining to research question 2 shows that low educational achievement and unplanned marriage are the consequences of teenage pregnancy. This finding is expected because a pregnant student supposed to withdraw from school immediately she is found to be pregnant. Pregnancy disrupts the educational career of the teenage girls, this may be temporary or permanent. Furthermore, teenage pregnancy hampers the mental prospect of the girls involved. A girl in this type of situation no longer marry the man of their dream, because they will be forced to marry any man available and willing to marry them at that point. Most parent portrays that attitude of disappointment on the teenager over pregnancy and by not supporting them financially. This finding are in-line with Eze (2021), who stated that the parents of the teenage girl may be disappointed and at such may decide to stop sponsoring her educations and social needs, because they see the previously help rendered or fees paid as wasted.

The finding pertaining to research question 3 indicates that the use of contraceptives, guidance and counseling and avoidance of bad friends are control measures to teenage pregnancy among female secondary school

students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area. This finding is expected because use of the fact that use of contraceptive ensures 70% protection of pregnancy. This finding disagree with Paul (2018), which stated that complete abstinence is a complete effective method for preventing conception.

Conclusions

From the findings of the studies it was concluded that peer group influence, poverty and lack of parental care are the principal factors responsible for teenage pregnancy among female secondary school students and that that use of contraceptives, guidance and counseling and avoidance of bad friends are the control measures to teenage pregnancy.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study.

1. Education through workshops and seminars on teenage pregnancy- causes, consequences and control measures- should be organized every term in schools for female secondary school students.
2. Religious leaders-should advocate more emphases on moral discipline through moral instruction, which can be delivered through teenage girls in the institution.
3. Health counselors should be assigned to every school and community so that they can give sex education to teenagers who are the vulnerable segment of the community,

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